

incidence.

The light trap was fitted with an ordinary tungsten 200-watt bulb in 1976 and 1979 and with an 80-watt mercury vapor lamp in 1977 and 1978. The light was on daily from 1800 to 0600 hours. The daily collection of stem borer moths was recorded.

The data show that first-generation moths were abundant in April-May (see figure). In June and the first fortnight of July, the population declined. From the second fortnight of July, until the end of August, the moths again increased. From September to November, emergence was at its lowest. But moth occurrence increased in December-January. From February to March, moth incidence was low.

In general, three abundant periods — April-May, July-August, and December-January — were noted. These periods synchronized with the productive phase of navarai crops, vegetative

Fluctuation of stem borer moth populations, 1976 to 1979. Tirur, India.

phase of sornavari crops, and productive density was strongly influenced by the phase of samba crops. Evidently moth local rice cropping pattern. ■

Evaluation of commercial and coded insecticides to control brown planthopper and green leafhopper

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One of the most serious problems in insect pest control is insecticide resistance. A countermeasure is the substitution of new insecticides. Continuous screening of newly developed insecticides is conducted in IRRI greenhouses and fields. In 1980, 23 compounds were screened as contact and foliar spray applications in the greenhouse against brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*.

Of the compounds tested, only cypermethrin, dioxacarb, M9918, M10604, NNI-750, UC27867, and UC54229 were effective against the brown planthopper and green leafhopper in Potter's spray tower and foliar application tests (see table). NNI-750, a growth regulator which kills the insect at molting, was effective against nymphs, but had no effect on adults. ■

Effectiveness of insecticides applied in the Potter's spray tower and as foliar spray against brown planthoppers (BPH) and green leafhoppers (GLH). IRRI, 1980.

Insecticide			Application method ^b			
			Potter's spray tower		Foliar spray	
Common name	Formulation	Group ^a	BPH	GLH	BPH	GLH
A-41286	48 EC		-	-	-	+
Agrotin 300	30 EC		-	-	-	-
Cypermethrin	10 EC	Pyrethroid	+	+	+	+
Dioxacarb	50 WP	Carbamate	+	+	+	+
Dioxathion	96 EC	Organophosphate	-	-	-	+
EXP5494	25 EC		+	-	-	-
M9918	20 OE		+	+	+	+
M10604	20 OE		+	+	+	+
Methidathion	40 EC	Organophosphate	-	+	+	+
Methiocarb	50 WP	Carbamate	-	-	+	+
NNI-750	50 WP		+	+	+	+
Pirimiphos methyl + carbophenothion	20 EC	Organophosphate	-	-	+	+
RP-32861	20 EC		+	+	-	-
SAN 285 AD	76 WP		-	-	-	-
SAN 2401	74 WP		-	-	-	-
Trichlorfon	95 SP	Organophosphate	-	-	-	-
U-56295	85 WP		-	-	-	-
U-57770	85 WP		-	-	-	-
UBI-W439-1265	50 WP		-	-	-	-
UC27867	50 WP	Carbamate	+	+	+	+
UC54229	100 Tech.	Carbamate	+	+	+	+
UC/MP 19779	48 EC	Carbamate	-	-	-	+
UC SF-1	40 F	Carbamate	-	+	+	+

^aComposition of several insecticides not available. ^b+ = ≥ 80% mortality 48 hours after spraying with Potter's spray tower and placing insects on foliar-treated plants.